

Principals' Disciplinary Techniques and Teachers' Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study was carried out to examine the extent of the relationship between principals' discipline techniques and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. To achieve this purpose, one objective, one research question and one null hypothesis were formulated to guide the study. Correlational research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised all 762 principals and 7,607 teachers drawn from the 254 public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The sample of this study consisted of 381 principals representing 50% of the population and 1,481 teachers representing 30% of the teaching population, giving a total of 1,862 respondents. A multistage sampling technique was adopted for the study, whereby purposive and stratified sampling techniques were used for the selection. Two researchers developed instruments tagged the Principals' Discipline Techniques Questionnaire (PDTQ) and the Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire (TJPQ), which were used for data collection. The validity of the instruments was established using the face validation method. The reliability of the instruments was established using the Cronbach alpha analysis method, which yielded reliability coefficients of .81 and .90 for the independent and the dependent variables, respectively. Regression coefficient was used to answer the research questions, while simple linear regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses at .05 level of significance. The results of the analyses revealed that discipline technique has a significant relationship with teachers' job performance. Based on the findings, it was recommended, among others, that principals should adopt stringent disciplinary measures in order to improve teachers' job performance.

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INTRODUCTION

Education is a vital tool for the development of any society. It ensures the acquisition of the necessary skills, orientation, knowledge and values required in everyday activities which are essential in the development of the society. In essence, the level of development of any society is a true reflection of its educational development.

In Nigeria, the belief of the citizens is that the higher the level of educational attainment, the better the conditions of living and the overall development of the citizens. Hence, education has been adopted as an instrument for effecting national development (FRN, 2013). The experienced societal vices, insurgencies, moral decadence, drug abuse, human trafficking, and political and religious crises are seen as effects of the low-level and poor-quality education. The quality of education that is obtainable in some of our public secondary schools is such that it barely equips the school leavers with the necessary skills to emancipate themselves from poverty and joblessness and foster societal development.

It has been observed that with the introduction of free and compulsory education, the public secondary schools are experiencing a tremendous increase in enrolment rate without a corresponding increase in teachers' employment and infrastructures, including the building of new schools to cater for the teeming student population. This has posed a serious challenge to the management of schools as well as teachers' job performance. Due to inadequate classroom accommodation, some schools at times resort to converting staff rooms to classrooms, making teachers unable to settle after lessons. This has made it sometimes impossible for proper supervision of teachers by the principals; some of them only come to schools when they have lessons and leave the school anytime they are tired of roaming. Unconducive learning environment with inadequate infrastructure may also pose a problem to the effective job performance of the teachers as well as a managerial challenge in terms of effective administration. In some schools, teachers could not evidently give their principals feedback with meaningful contributions that may help the growth of the school system; some principals seldom communicate with their teachers on the way forward as a result of poor working conditions and at times due to unnecessary bureaucratic principles which may not allow a free flow of information, thus reducing teachers' morale and thus affecting their performance.

The success or failure of any school system depends to a large extent on the managers (principals), teachers, their quality, their commitment to duty and their

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effectiveness on the job. The task of bringing about desired learning outcomes in the learners to achieve a nation's goal of education rests on principals' and teachers' competences. The overall school's performance depends largely on management effectiveness and teachers' commitment to work.

The management techniques of the principal as a chief administrator of the secondary school could play a significant role in determining the level of teachers' performance and commitment to teaching, which in turn could enhance learning processes and outcomes. Management techniques are systematic and analytical methods used to assist in decision-making, the improvement of efficiency and effectiveness and, in particular, the conduct of the two key managerial activities of planning and control (Heine 2010). Management techniques as tools that managers use to keep positive team morale, improve productivity and develop new talents. It involves helping to boost employees' morale to work towards organisational goal attainment. It consists of specified and often sequential methods of tackling a problem, providing information for decision-making or improving operational efficiency. Iwhiwhu (2010) maintained that management techniques deal with every aspect of a situation that describes possible measures for goal achievement.

Obviously, principals' management techniques may not be effective without a corresponding effort by teachers' performance, which entails the discharge of obligatory functions that are task-orientated and aimed at achieving defined goals (Asiyai, 2005). Teachers' performance is encompassing, as it involves the discharge of some defined tasks necessary to bring about desirable teaching and learning outcomes. Such tasks include classroom management aimed at effective and efficient utilisation of available human and material resources for the attainment of organisational goals. The classroom teacher is charged with lots of functions to perform in the teaching and learning processes. One of the most challenging tasks is classroom management and control. The teachers' effectiveness in teaching is assessed by the ability to use varied classroom management techniques to direct students towards effective and meaningful learning during instruction. Meaningful teaching and learning cannot be achieved in a classroom environment characterised by rowdiness, crowdedness, noise-making and distractions (Oyira, 2004). Educational objectives cannot be fully achieved without the use of a conducive classroom environment since the classroom is the meeting point for both teachers and students where curricular activities are implemented.

Close observation of our public secondary schools across the state does not depict conducive classroom situations. Teachers are made to teach in a class of 80-100

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students at a time, in violation of the mandatory teacher-student ratio of 1:40 recommended by the National Policy on Education (FRN 2013). These crowded classes could sometimes lead to ineffectiveness of teachers in their job performance. Other teachers' tasks include lesson preparation and presentation, students' continuous assessment and evaluation, administration of examinations, improvisation/use of instructional materials, completion of scheme of work, introduction of innovations for lesson comprehension and retention, and presentation of results, among others. A good number of the teachers' tasks are executed in the classroom with the use of necessary infrastructure, which must be inevitably available before teaching and learning processes can flow. However, it is evident that the number of teachers in our secondary schools is grossly inadequate, facilities are either unavailable or not enough, accommodation is insufficient to cater for the teeming student population, some structures are dilapidated with no replacement, new schools are not being built to ease the overcrowding problem, and a lot more could likely reduce teachers' morale, affect general cooperation with school authority, discourage meaningful contributions and in turn could lead to poor job performance.

Deductively, measurement of teachers' performance seems to be based on two criteria, namely, the effectiveness paradigm, which uses students' outcome (usually achievement), and the teaching process paradigm, which focuses on various aspects of teachers' and students' behaviour judged to be worthwhile in their own right or linked to students' achievement (Iyede, 2001). Evaluating teachers' performance using the performance criterion has attracted much attention. In Nigeria, the general belief is that performing teachers must produce performing students. Poor academic performance of students in Nigeria has therefore been linked to poor teachers' performance in terms of accomplishing the teaching task, negative attitude to work and poor teaching habits, which have been attributed to poor management (Ofoegbu, 2004).

As a leader in the school system, the principal's administrative competence in the areas of supervision, communication, mentoring, decision-making, capacity building, disciplinary measures, conflict management, and others could be adopted as management techniques which may be important in directing the thrust, dynamics and trends of teaching and learning in secondary schools. Thus, the overall school administration is tested by these variables.

Disciplinary measures are those steps taken by a school administrator to ensure compliance with school rules and regulations. The principal, as the manager of the school, is vested with the responsibility of instilling discipline among teachers. The

term 'discipline' in an organisation implies meaningful co-ordination and control of personnel which prompts that organisation to conform to the prescribed code of conduct framed for their guidance (Reddy, 2004). Discipline aims at establishing a human relations climate based on mutual trust, confidence and respect in superior-subordinate working relationships. Jucious (2008) maintained that discipline is said to be good when employees willingly follow the rules of their superiors.

Where principals neglect the aspect of discipline in schools, teachers show a high rate of absenteeism, lateness to work, dereliction of duty, insubordination, disrespect to constituted authority, laxity and a high rate of attrition, which inhibits proper teaching and completion of the scheme of work and projects a bad example for students who may look on teachers as role models. With proper disciplinary measures, teachers stand the ground of discharging their duties effectively.

Research Hypothesis

To guide the study, the following null hypothesis was formulated:

H₀: There is no significant relationship between principals' disciplinary techniques and teachers' job performance in Akwa Ibom State.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Design of the Study

The correlational research design was adopted for this study. This design was considered appropriate as it sought to measure the existing relationship between the independent variable (principals' management techniques) and the dependent variable (teachers' job performance). In this type of design, it is both impracticable and unethical for the researcher to manipulate any of the variables; rather, the emphasis is on describing the natural course of events as they occur (McCombes, 2009). The study, therefore, aimed to determine the extent of the relationship between the independent and dependent variables.

Population of the Study

The population of this study comprised all principals, vice principals (academic), and vice principals (administration/special duties), totalling 762, as well as all 7,607 teachers in the 254 public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State during the

2019/2020 academic session (SEB, 2019).

Sample and Sampling Technique

A multistage sampling technique was employed for this study. Purposive, stratified, and cluster sampling methods were used to include vice principals of academics, administration, and special duties, owing to their administrative responsibilities, alongside principals. Public secondary schools were stratified across the three senatorial districts of the state. Within each district, schools were clustered into local government areas, taking into account the number of schools, principals, and teachers in each zone. This yielded:

- **Senatorial Districts:** 9, 12, and 10 Local Government Areas, respectively
- **Public Secondary Schools:** 89, 72, and 93
- **Principals:** 89, 72, and 93
- **Teachers:** 3,453, 1,294, and 2,860, respectively

From this distribution, simple random sampling was applied to select 160 public secondary schools (representing 50% of the population across the senatorial districts), 381 principals (50%), and 1,481 teachers (30%). This produced a total sample size of 1,862 respondents.

To ensure adequate representation, at least 12 teachers were sampled in each school. Each principal rated a minimum of four teachers, while four teachers rated each principal. This established a principal–teacher ratio of 1:4 and a teacher–principal ratio of 4:1. (See Appendix I for the sampling frame).

Instrumentation

Two research instruments were developed by the researcher to generate data:

i. Principals' Discipline Techniques Questionnaire (PDTQ)

- Designed to measure principals' management techniques, focusing on seven sub-variables.
- Each category comprised eight items, yielding a total of 56 items.
- The PDTQ was rated by teachers.

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ii. Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire (TJPQ)

- Developed to measure indicators of teachers' performance such as classroom management, lesson delivery, student evaluation, introduction of innovations, and mastery of lesson content.
- The TJPQ contained 20 items.
- The TJPQ was rated by principals.

Method of Data Analysis

The regression coefficient was employed to answer the research questions, while simple linear regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses. All hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

Hypothesis

There is no significant relationship between principals' disciplinary techniques and teachers' job performance in Akwa Ibom State.

Simple regression analysis was used to test the null hypothesis and summary data shown in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1: Simple regression analysis of relationship between principals' disciplinary technique and teachers' job performance

Variables	Source of Variable	SS	Df	MS	F-value	P-value	Decision p<.05
Principals'	Regression	236637.903	1	236637.903	disciplinary	Technique	
Teachers' job performance	Residual	434801.012	1421	305982	773.37	.000	Significant
Total		671438.915	1422				

Significant P<.05 *Source: Researcher field work (2021).*

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The result in Table 4.1 reveals that the calculated F-value was 773.371 and the calculated P-value was .000, which was less than the F-value at the .05 level of significance with 1422 degrees of freedom. With this result, the null hypothesis, which stated that the extent of the relationship between principals' disciplinary technique and teachers' job performance is not significant, was rejected. Hence, the extent of the relationship between principals' disciplinary technique and teachers' job performance is significant.

Discussion of Findings

The main focus of this study was to determine the extent of the relationship between principals' disciplinary techniques and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State. From the findings of the research, it has been revealed that the extent of the relationship between principals' management techniques and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State is significant. The following discussions presented below are based on the results of the hypotheses raised in the study.

Disciplinary Technique and Teachers' Job Performance

The extent of the relationship between principals' disciplinary technique and teachers' job performance is significant. The direction of this finding gives credence to the fact that discipline is important in ensuring that school objectives are achieved and that teachers behave well in consonance with school rules and regulations as well as teachers' professional ethics. This result is eminent considering the role of discipline in educational institutions; it affects the achievement of educational objectives. The finding agrees with the views of Chisholm (2007), "that disciplined teachers produce disciplined learners and positively impact on the overall school goals attainment".

In a study by Nguni (2005) on the relationship between teachers' perception of the behaviour of the school organisation and the teachers' perception of discipline relating to organisational effectiveness, a random sampling of 250 teachers each from 10 secondary schools randomly selected from the metropolitan Nashville public school system received questionnaires. 159 of those randomly selected teachers participated in the study and returned their completed questionnaire. The specimen rank co-efficient of correlation product was used for organising and summarising the data and thereby determining the level of discipline. Based on the findings, it was concluded that a

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relationship existed between managerial techniques and perception of discipline effectiveness. Also, there was a relationship between the psychological state of people who work in school organisations and their perception of discipline effectiveness. Teachers working in school organisations which are intellectually supportive or structured and work-orientated seem to perceive the prevailing discipline in the school as effective. It is likely that an unhealthy school environment is related to the high incidence of poor teacher job performance.

This implies that teachers are meant to be role models to their learners and that the level of comportment and decency in behaviour exhibited by teachers has a direct influence on students and the school's success at large.

This finding is in tandem with the position of Cabanes (2017:44), “that a principal that uses supportive discipline, corrective discipline, verbal and written warnings where necessary and appropriate sanctions on erring teachers within prescribed policy is bound to create a humorous and enabling atmosphere for effective learning, and achievement of desirable outcomes becomes obvious.” This entails that a disciplined teacher is bound to produce a quality service for improved job performance.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that principals' disciplinary techniques have a significant relationship with teachers' job performance. Discipline serves as an essential mechanism for guiding teachers' professional conduct, ensuring compliance with institutional rules and regulations, and promoting the attainment of educational objectives. Consequently, effective application of disciplinary measures by school principals enhances teachers' job performance and contributes to the overall success of the school system.

Since principals' disciplinary techniques exert a significant influence on teachers' job performance, school leaders should ensure that appropriate sanctions are consistently imposed on erring teachers within the framework of established policies. Such sanctions should serve both as corrective measures and deterrents to others, thereby fostering professionalism, accountability, and improved teacher performance.

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